

EDUCATIONAL AFFAIRS AT TASHKENT STATE UNIVERSITY OF LAW

Amirov Elbek Egamberdi ugli

Doctoral student of Karshi State University
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Abstract: This article historically analyzes the history of the Tashkent State Law University, which is considered the main center for training legal personnel in Uzbekistan, and the state of educational work in it.

Key words: Tashkent State Law University (TSLU), Turkestan People's University, People's Commissariat of Justice, European Credit System, ECTS.

Tashkent State Law University (TSU) is the main higher educational and scientific-methodological institution in Uzbekistan for the training of legal personnel. The history of the university begins on April 21, 1918, when the legal department was established on the basis of the socio-economic faculty at Turkestan People's University. This was the first step in creating a law school in Central Asia, especially in Uzbekistan. From 1918 to the 1990s, this law school underwent a number of changes as an institution under the People's Commissariat of Justice of the UZSSR [1].

On August 15, 1991, according to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers, it was separated from Tashkent State University under the name of Tashkent State Legal Institute. Since then, this educational institution has become an integral part of the legal field, which embodies the concept of unity of education, science and practice.

By the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 28, 2013 PQ-1990, Tashkent State Legal Institute was transformed into Tashkent State Law University [1].

The educational process at the university is based on the credit-module system, which is a new system in our country. European credit system - ECTS (European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System) was introduced, providing students with the opportunity to choose subjects.

From this 2020/2021 academic year, the university is accepting bachelor's and master's degrees in the form of distance education. The university is introducing joint educational programs that provide a "double degree".

Students are given the opportunity to choose elective subjects, special attention is paid to the issue of their independent learning, and 60% of the study load is allocated to independent education of students in the curriculum.

Science programs (syllabi) are prepared in 3 languages (Uzbek, Russian, English) based on the experience of higher education institutions that are in the top 300 international rankings and introduced into the educational process. The percentage of non-specialist subjects was reduced from 22% to 10%.

In the 2020/2021 academic year, the number of specialized subjects taught in a foreign language was 35. 23 special academic groups where all subjects are taught in English have been established [2].

35 specialized subjects and 5 non-specialized subjects are taught in a foreign language in the fields of undergraduate education and master's degrees. This specialty makes up 34 percent of all (104) specialty disciplines being taught (in 2019, it was 2 or 6.9%).

In order to connect the educational process with direct practice, departments of practical jurisprudence were established at the Supreme Court, the General Prosecutor's Office (at the Academy of the General Prosecutor's Office), the Ministry of Internal Affairs (at the Ministry of Internal Affairs Training Institute), and the Intellectual Property Agency.

Special attention has been paid to the use of information and communication technologies in the organization of the educational process. In particular, from the 2020/2021 academic year distant.tsul.uz based on MOODLE-object-oriented dynamic learning environment (December 10, 2021). distance education platform was launched [2].

Today, 4,426 students are studying at the bachelor's level, and 269 students are studying at the master's level. Classes are held in Uzbek, Russian and English.

Within the framework of joint educational programs, an agreement was reached with the Grodno State University named after Yanka Kupala of the Republic of Belarus on international private law, and with the KAZGYU University of the Republic of Kazakhstan named after M.S. Narikbaev on the training of bachelors in the field of education "International Economic Law". .

Also, negotiations are underway with Turkey's Ankara Bayazid Yildirim University and Poland's Warsaw University on the issue of establishing joint educational programs.

In order to ensure transparency in TDYU, to provide convenience for students and teachers, it envisages digitization of the educational process, including the formation of the schedule of classes, conducting exams, evaluation, formation of student ratings and the introduction of the transition to electronic document exchange. The "E-University" platform is being launched. This

platform allows students and their parents, the general public to monitor and directly participate in all processes related to the university's activities, and ensures that the processes are open and transparent.

Prevention and fight against corruption is one of the main tasks of the university. In this context, the University adopted a program to combat corruption.

The Commission for Combating Corruption was established. A Code of Ethics was also developed. Creating a feedback system for receiving information about the facts of corruption, conducting surveys among students on corruption issues on a systematic basis and taking practical measures based on their results, the public over the examination process control mechanisms are being introduced.

TDYU became a full member of international organizations such as International Association of Universities (IAU), International Association of Law Schools (IALS), European Law Faculties Association (ELFA) . Currently, applications for membership in the Magna Charta of Universities and the European Association of Higher Education Institutions (EURASHE) have been submitted [3].

Also, a center for professional training of legal personnel according to international standards, a specialized branch of the university for training and upgrading the qualifications of preventive inspectors, and an academic lyceum at the university are also operating at the university.

At the same time, the activities of legal technical schools of the Ministry of Justice established in each region of our republic are being coordinated by the university.

5 faculties, 19 departments and 2 foreign law centers are operating in TDYU from the 2021/2022 academic year. There are 11 specializations in the master's degree [2].

Education at the university is conducted in three languages: Uzbek, Russian, English. To study in English, a student must have an IELTS certificate, which determines the level of English language proficiency, or have passed an English language test at the university itself.

At the undergraduate level of the university, personnel are trained in the following educational programs (directions):

State legal activity

Civil and Business Law

Criminal legal activity

International law and comparative jurisprudence

State Administration

Jurisprudence (External)

The university cooperates with the military department of the National University of Uzbekistan. After completing education at the military department of UzMU, students will receive the military rank of reserve lieutenant.

For the academic year 2023/2024, the entrance exams of the Tashkent State Law University's bachelor's degree in full-time education were passed in 5 subjects. The complex of sciences consists of 2 parts.

The first is mandatory for all test-takers in three subjects - Mother tongue (Uzbek, Russian, Karakalpak and other languages) 1.1 points for each correct answer for 10 test questions (total 33 points), Mathematics for each 10 test questions 1.1 points for one correct answer (33 points in total), 1.1 points for each correct answer (33 points in total) for 10 test questions on the history of Uzbekistan.

The second - two subjects suitable for undergraduate education - Law with 3.1 points for each correct answer for 30 test items (total 93 points) and Foreign Language for 2.1 points for each correct answer for 30 test items (total 63 points) is evaluated. Maximum score in 5 subjects — 189 [2]

Admission of foreign citizens to the undergraduate program of TDYU is carried out without tests, according to the results of the interview held at the university and taking into account the points collected in accordance with the rating system (studying is only on the basis of a contract).

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